

DISAC

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Deliverable 1.1

Quality Plan

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Deliverable D1.1 Quality Plan

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Abstract

The deliverable introduces the 6G-DISAC quality plan, providing an overview of the project's structure and processes to ensure result quality. It aims to establish common guidelines for progress reports, document handling, quality assurance policies, including project goals, and implement a risk management procedure to support these objectives.

Keywords

Quality plan, quality, project management, organisation, deliverables, internal reports, milestones, reporting, confidentiality, publications, risk management, management structure.

Disclaimer

This work has been performed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project 6G-DISAC co-funded by the EU. This information reflects the consortium's view, but the consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. This deliverable has been submitted to the EU commission, but it has not been reviewed and it has not been accepted by the EU commission yet.

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Table 1-1 List of Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Description	Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence	PC	Project Coordinator
BS	Base Station	PMT	Project Management Team
CA	Consortium Agreement	PoC	Proof of Concept
EC	European Commission	RAT	Radio Access Technologies
EMF	Electromagnetic Field	RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
GA	Grant Agreement	SLAM	Similtaneous Localisation And Mapping
IM	Innovation Manager	TL	Task Leader
ISAC	Integrated Sensing And Communica-tion	TM	Technical Manager
KPI	Key Performance Indicator	WP	Work Package
mMIMO	massive Multiple Input Multiple Output	WPL	Work Package Leader
Partner abbreviations			
CEA	Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives		
CHA	Chalmers Tekniska Hoegskola Ab		
NOK	Nokia Networks		
TIM	Telecom Italia Spa		
Orange	Orange Sa		
NKUA	Ethniko Kai Kapodistriako Panepistimio Athinon		
IMS	Institut Polytechnique De Bordeaux		
NEC	Nec Laboratories Europe Gmbh		
BOS	Robert Bosch Gmbh		
RAD	Radchat Ab		

1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the 6G-DISAC quality plan. It aims to serve as an overview of the project structure and to explain the setup and processes targeting the quality of the delivered results. Through this deliverable, the 6G-DISAC consortium will establish a common understanding of the guidelines to be adopted for making of progress reports (such as internal reports and deliverables), documents handling and procedures, to define the quality assurance policy, including quality goals for the project, and to create a risk management procedure for guarantee an infrastructure to support the above. It is complimentary to the grant agreement (GA) and the consortium agreement (CA).

The document consists of five sections: starting with the introduction, section 2 provides details on the roles and responsibilities of the project organisation. Section 3 details the process for the deliverables and internal reports preparation, how the project is organised, and how meetings are arranged. Sections 4 outline details the document handling process within the project. Section 5 dives into the quality assurance process and risk handling aspect of the project.

2 Project organisation

This section offers an overview of the project organisation. The 6G-DISAC project consortium comprises ten partners, from five different European countries, as showed in Figure 2-1. In particular, the consortium includes two network equipment vendors (Nokia and NEC), two telecom operators (Orange and TIM), three universities (Chalmers, NKUA and IMS Bordeaux), one research and technology organisation (CEA), one vertical (Bosh), and one small medium enterprise (RadChat).

Figure 2-1 6G-DISAC project consortium

2.1 Structure of the management

The 6G-DISAC project consortium conceived the management structure to ensure an open and productive dialogue between partners on scientific and strategic issues, while making quick and

effective decisions on technical or organisational matters, in conformity with the Funding authorities' contractual requests (Figure 2-2). The roles and responsibilities within 6G-DISAC are discussed in more details in the following sections.

Figure 2-2 6G-DISAC project management structure

2.1.1 Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team (PMT) consists of the Project Coordinator (PC), the Technical Manager (TM), the Innovation Manager (IM) and the Work Package Leaders WPLs. The procedures for making decision will be set in a Consortium Agreement on a basis of a text approved by the partners based on European standard agreements, amended to guarantee efficient governance of the Consortium and approved by the Funding Authorities. The PMT will be responsible of:

- Continuous reviewing the project vision, in the light of the results of the project, of other pertinent scientific, technological, standardisation or market developments and of the long-term policies of the Funding Authorities and of the Project Partners.
- Continuously defining and reviewing orientations for specific research activities within the project.
- Planning of the overall technical activities and ensuring that the work in the Work Packages (WPs) is in line with the project plan.
- Discussing and solving problems among partners or WPs.
- Defining plans for the extension and exploitation of research carried out within the framework of the project.
- Assuring the quality of all deliverables and dissemination material.

2.1.2 Work Package Leader (WPL)

The Work Package leader will be in charge of the daily management of the technical work in their respective WP. The WPL is responsible for:

- Planning and organising the WP activities, including scheduling of regular meetings.
- Monitoring progress of individual Work Packages and continuously coordinating the technical work.
- Maintaining a good level of exchanges between the WP in order to align contributions and make the project providing with some coherent overall outcomes.
- Reporting technical progress to the PMT in regular reports.
- Trigger and coordinate cross WP discussion topics.

2.1.3 Project Coordinator (PC)

The project coordinator is responsible for the overall communication, administration, legal, and coordination of the project. The PC is in charge of:

- Managing contacts with the funding authorities, providing reports and deliverables as agreed.
- Planning project meetings, relations and dissemination.
- Monitoring the quality and risk management
- Coordinating together with WPLs dependencies between various WPs and tasks as well as reviewing and approving of reports and deliverables.

2.1.4 Technical Manager (TM)

The Technical manager is responsible for coordinating and promoting the technical work of the project. The TM has to lead the technical activities in order to ensure the technical project objectives and results are timely achieved.

2.1.5 Innovation Manager (IM)

The Innovation Manager (IM) is responsible for managing the project's innovation monitoring the research results and identifying the exploitable assets provided by the project. The IM is also responsible for the activities related to the marketing of the outcomes of the project developing business exploitation actions.

2.1.6 Task Leader (TL)

The Task Leader (TL) will be in charge of the daily management of the technical work in the respective tasks. The TL will be responsible for reporting any issue to the WPL, which may affect the WP work, and the WPL can assist TL to overcome these and ensure the success of project's outcomes.

2.1.7 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The External Advisory Board consists of experts who have the qualification and experience to provide valuable insights and advice on the strategic direction of the project. Furthermore, the EAB member monitor the technical development and activities throughout the 6G-DISAC project duration, and offer consultation to the consortium to ensuring the high quality of outcomes and results. The specific role of the EAB is outlined in the Consortium Agreement.

2.2 Work Packages and Organisation

The 6G-DISAC project comprises 6 work packages spanning the 3-year project duration. Figure 2-3 describes the relations between WPs and related tasks.

2.2.1 Structure of the Work Packages

The 6G-DISAC project consortium has created a work plan in the aim of achieving the high technical and scientific goals. This work plan provides the principal activity of technical research and is composed of six WPs. Specifically, WP1 deals with project and technical management.

Figure 2-3 6G-DISAC PERT CHART

WPs 2-5 are the technical work packages, covering aspects related to use cases, architectures, waveforms, signal processing, resource allocation, and demonstrations. WP6 covers the dissemination, exploitation, and standardisation. The WPs are listed and detailed hereafter.

WP1: Project Management (Leader: CEA; start/end month: 1-36) will undertake all project coordination activities, interfacing with the European Commission (EC), day-to-day project coordination, contract and financial management, quality control and knowledge management, and

participation in 5GPPP Infrastructure Meetings. The main outputs of WP1 are the project handbook, general overview of the project progress, and 5GPPP joint activities.

WP2: Distributed ISAC uses cases, metrics, and architecture (*Leader: Orange; start/end month: 1-24*) will select and define scenarios and use cases relevant for Distributed Sensing and Communication. It will also define the metrics and KPIs for the selected scenarios and use cases. WP2 is also responsible for defining the architectural extensions needed to support these scenarios and use cases. The main outputs of WP2 are a report on scenarios, use cases and KPIs, and a description of 6G-DISAC architecture.

WP3: Physical layer implications and enablers of integrated sensing and communications (*Leader: CHA; start/end month: 1-36*) will develop and analyse physical-layer solutions in terms of waveforms and signal processing algorithms for distributed integrated communication and sensing, utilising model-based and AI-based (including semantic) approaches. It will also identify and harness technological enablers (e.g., RIS, mMIMO, full duplex) to improve sensing and sensing-aided communication.

WP4: Resource allocation for ISAC and new distributed and cooperative sensing (*Leader: NEC; start/end month: 7-36*) will develop novel scalable and flexible resource allocation schemes, as well as distributed computing frameworks that enable ISAC. It will study the inherent trade-off between communication and sensing to find a suitable balance in dynamic environments, while respecting heterogeneous hardware constraints of the involved devices. Moreover, it will develop advanced spectrum management schemes enabling distributed ISAC operations across different RATs.

WP5: Evaluation through Proof-of-Concepts and Demonstrators (*Leader: BOS; start/end month: 13-36*) will validate and verify the algorithms and concepts developed in the other work packages by demonstrations. The WP will combine different hardware setup to demonstrate the individual components of DISAC. The demonstrators are intended to be developed in parallel. In the end, based on an umbrella use case, i.e., a smart and connected intersection, the components are brought together and demonstrated in a practical real-world scenario.

WP6: Dissemination, exploitation, and standardisation (*Leader: NKUA; start/end month: 1-36*) will coordinate outputs from all WPs to disseminate the outcomes of the project in the form of top-level publications, conferences, workshops, special sessions, and tutorials, as well as to contribute towards standardisation in 3GPP, ITU, and ETSI. Additionally, WP6 is also responsible to put in place a results exploitation plan for industry and relevant business. The WP6 outputs are the dissemination activities, standardisation of ISAC systems and schemes, and an industrial exploitation plan.

2.2.2 Work packages objectives

The objectives of WP1 are:

- **O1.1** management, coordination, quality assurance and impact management activities of the project
- **O1.2** ensure a successful completion of the project goals on time, within the budget and having the expected impacts achieved.
- **O1.3** general project management activities: organisation of meetings, reporting, facilitating communication and coordination processes and tools as well as the financial management of the project and providing interfaces to the EC.

The objectives of WP2 are:

- **O2.1** Identify reference scenarios and relevant use cases, which benefit most from distributed sensing (multiple BSs, multiple sensors of different functionalities and computation capabilities, multiple targets, cooperation, ...) and those where communication can benefit from sensing.
- **O2.2** Define metrics and KPIs, which are needed for analysing distributed and intelligent sensing and communications.
- **O2.3** Investigate and define the architecture for distributed integrated sensing and communication systems, including network functions, elements and corresponding interfaces.

The objectives of WP3 are:

- **O3.1** To develop adaptive and semantic-aware waveforms for distributed ISAC, provide flexibility and adaptability in support of different demands and requirements.
- **O3.2** To develop scalable algorithms for distributed and cooperative sensing and localisation, including radio SLAM, leveraging the technological enablers. Exploit high resolution in time, space, and frequency to detect and track objects / users with extremely high precision.
- **O3.3** To design communication techniques leveraging sensing and contextual information, providing net gains in terms of communication performance metrics.

The objectives of WP4 are:

- **O4.1** To design innovative distributed protocols that enable efficient ISAC, by suitably fusing information sensed by possibly massive numbers of networks nodes of different types, exploiting the associated contextual information for communication optimisation.
- **O4.2** To develop goal-oriented resource allocation and orchestration schemes based on contextual information that allow for computation offloading, over-the-air computation, and computing splitting approaches from end devices to the cloud.
- **O4.3** To develop novel efficient spectrum management techniques based on spectrum sensing, which allow to pursue: *i)* energy consumption minimisation of the overall network, *ii)* EMF exposure reduction, and *iii)* efficient optimisation of the communication parameters.
- **O4.4** To design distributed multi-RAT sensing technologies that exploit fusions of sensed data from multiple heterogeneous sensors to enhance targets' sensing as well as to contribute to the optimisation of the communication parameters.

The objectives of WP5 are:

- **O5.1** Define all needed configurations to be tested and perform the necessary development or adaptations of the PoCs for distributed sensing, including pre-processing and data recording means.
- **O5.2** Demonstrate the capability of simultaneous sensing and communication, and the flexibility to adapt the number of available resources for sensing and communication based on requirements, including positioning using SLAM.
- **O5.3** Test and compare different adaptive and semantic-aware waveforms for distributed ISAC as analysed in O3.1.
- **O5.4** Implement the algorithms, resource allocation techniques, and protocols interfacing to the demonstrators.

The objectives of WP6 are:

- **O6.1** To communicate and disseminate the project results and vision to a wider audience, and to maximise the potential of adoption of the project results, and the overall impact of the project (Task 6.1);
- **O6.2** To facilitate interaction with other related projects and activities in industry, academia, and society as a whole, and to use the project results for training and education purposes (Task 6.1);
- **O6.3** To give the project consortium a clear picture of the project’s main interests and most important results in order to enforce exploitation of the project results, especially for the industrial partners (Task 6.2);
- **O6.4** To identify the needs for standardisation for DISAC networks and ensure the introduction of the project results in relevant standardisation activities (Task 6.3);
- **O6.5** Organise a dedicated final event (6G-DISAC final workshop) to disseminate the project results consolidated through the project trials and to contribute to the social acceptance of B5G/6G future technologies.

2.2.3 Work packages management

Table 2-1 Project Management Team

Role	6G-DISAC Project Management Team	
Project Coordinator	Emilio Calvanese Strinati	(CEA)
Technical Manager	Henk Wymeersch	(CHA)
Innovation Manager	Philippe Sehier	(NOK)
WP1 Leader	Emilio Calvanese Strinati	(CEA)
WP2 Leader	Giyarpuram Madhusudan	(Orange)
WP3 Leader	Henk Wymeersch	(CHA)
WP4 Leader	Placido Mursia	(NEC)
WP5 Leader	Maximilian Stark	(BOS)
WP6 Leader	George Alexandropoulos	(NKUA)

Table 2-2 Project Task Leaders

WP	Task	6G-DISAC project team	
1	1.1	Emilio Calvanese Strinati	(CEA)
	1.2	Henk Wymeersch	(CHA)
	1.3	Philippe Sehier	(NOK)
2	2.1	Maximilian Stark	(BOS)
	2.2	Placido Mursia	(NEC)
	2.3	Giyarpuram Madhusudan	(Orange)
3	3.1	Emilio Calvanese Strinati	(CEA)
	3.2	Furkan Keskin	(CHA)
	3.3	George Alexandropoulos	(NKUA)
4	4.1	Placido Mursia	(NEC)
	4.2	Emilio Calvanese Strinati	(CEA)
	4.3	George Alexandropoulos	(NKUA)
5	5.1	Philippe Sehier	(NOK)
	5.2	Maximilian Stark	(BOS)
6	6.1	George Alexandropoulos	(NKUA)
	6.2	Maximilian Stark	(BOS)
	6.3	Philippe Sehier	(NOK)

2.3 Reference Documents

Two contractual documents define the obligations and rights that apply to all entities involved in the 6G-DISAC project:

- **Grant Agreement (GA)** defining the legal obligations agreed between the European Commission and the coordinator, and acceded by the consortium partners. The GA specifies the rights, obligations, terms and conditions of the consortium beneficiaries for carrying out actions.
- **Consortium Agreement (CA)** defining the relations between the partners of the consortium, and their rights and obligations. The CA is jointly accepted and signed by all consortium beneficiaries and will be in effect until the complete fulfilment of the obligations explained in the GA.

3 Project Management Processes

3.1 Deliverable and internal reports

The work plan is organised into three partially overlapping phases. Phase 1 relates to the initial work and covers the first half of the project. After 1 year, phase 2 starts, developing the technical solutions and demonstrators. The last half of the project relates to phase 3 and covers the final solutions and demonstrations. Figure 3-1 represents the corresponding Gantt chart.

Figure 3-1 6G-DISAC Gantt chart

3.1.1 Reporting Periods

In the project proposal, *MX* indicates the delivery dates of the 6G-DISAC project’s deliverables, stating that the reporting period ends the last day of the month *X*. Table 3-1 lists all the deliverables expected from 6G-DISAC project, and Table 3-2 specifies the *Milestones*.

Table 3-1 List of project deliverables (PU=public)

No.	Deliverable name	WP	Lead	Dissemination level	Date
D1.1	Quality plan	1	CEA	PU	M03
D1.2	Initial Data Management Plan	1	CEA	PU	M04
D1.3	First project management periodic report	1	CEA	PU	M18
D1.4	Data Management Plan	1	CEA	PU	M33
D1.5	Final project management report	1	CEA	PU	M36
D2.1	Preliminary version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs	2	BOS	PU	M12
D2.2	Preliminary version of the distributed ISAC architecture	2	Orange	PU	M12
D2.3	Final version of scenarios, use cases and KPIs	2	NOK	PU	M18
D2.4	Final version of the distributed ISAC architecture	2	Orange	PU	M24
D3.1	Initial solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC	3	CEA	PU	M18
D3.2	Intermediate solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC	3	NKUA	PU	M30
D3.3	Final solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC	3	CHA	PU	M36
D4.1	Initial specifications for protocols and orchestration solutions	4	NKUA	PU	M18
D4.2	Intermediate specifications for protocols, orchestration solution, and spectrum management	4	NEC	PU	M30
D4.3	Final specifications for protocols, orchestration solution, and spectrum management	4	TIM	PU	M36
D5.1	Key Components and Integration	5	BOS	PU	M18
D5.2	Selection of components for demonstrations and measurement campaign	5	NEC	PU	M24
D5.3	Results from 6G-DISAC demonstrations	5	NOK	PU	M33

D5.4	Final evaluation report	5	BOS	PU	M36
D6.1	Dissemination and project website	6	NKUA	PU	M04
D6.2	Standardisation action plan	6	NOK	PU	M06
D6.3	Intermediate dissemination and standardisation activity report	6	NOK	PU	M18
D6.4	Final report on exploitation of knowledge and results	6	BOS	PU	M36
D6.5	Final dissemination and standardisation activity report	6	NEC	PU	M36

Table 3-2 List of project Milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Related work package(s)	Due date (in month)	Means of verification
M1	Project website, social media launched	WP6	M04	D6.1, D1.1, public website available
M2	6G-DISAC vision: Use cases, KPIs, requirements	WP2	M12	D2.1
M3	Initial technical results and review	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	M18	D1.3, D2.3, D3.1, D4.1, D5.1, D6.3
M4	Intermediate project results for demonstration	WP3, WP4	M30	D3.2, D4.2
M5	Final reporting and review, consolidation of dissemination, standardisation and exploitation	WP1, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6	M36	D1.5, D3.3, D4.3, D5.4, D6.4, D6.5

3.1.2 Reviewing and submission Processes

Each of the deliverables goes through a review process to ensure the high quality and technical level output of the 6g-DISAC project. At latest three months before the deliverable’s deadline *MX*, the deliverable editor proposes the table of contents to the correspondent WP contributors. Following, the editor provides a skeleton document of the deliverable and assigns responsible partners for each section. The WPL will be responsible, together with the deliverable editor, to provide a stable draft of the document, efficiently edited and containing all the expected inputs from WP contributors. The deliverable editors will send the *Draft_V1.0* of the deliverable to start the following review process (also shown in Figure 3-2):

1. Internal review: the editor and two other partners involved in the WP, revise the deliverable (one-week process).
2. External review: the revised document is available to two reviewers external to the WP, or not mainly involved, to provide comments (two weeks process).
3. Revision phase: the editor starts addressing the review comments and update the document (one-week process).
4. PC and TM review: the revised document is available to the PC and the TM for final review and proof-reading, a further revision should be required to the editor (two weeks process).
5. The PC submits the final version of the deliverable to the European Commission.

Figure 3-2 Review process timeline for deliverables and internal reports

3.2 Project reports

The advancement of the project must be closely supervised in order to quickly detect difficulties and find appropriate solutions.

3.2.1 Internal reporting

The PMT establishes monthly virtual meetings to report the technical and management project work done, listing difficulties and challenges, milestones and deliverables (or contributions to deliverables in case of joint deliverables) that have been reached, patents and publications. In particular, each WPL reports the progress and achievements of the work towards the objectives of the project.

3.2.2 Continuous EC reporting

The PC is responsible for periodical reporting to the EC. The online grant management system Sygma can be utilised, together with general templates provided by the EC, according to the reporting periods specified in the project proposal.

3.2.3 Periodical EC reporting

These intermediate reports, previously described, will make it possible to simplify the overall required reviews. The status of the project will be presented every 18 months, so *M18* and *M36* for a complete review of carried-out works. They provide in detail the status of each Work Package. These reports will be prepared under the supervision of the project Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders.

A financial and technical periodic report must be submitted within sixty (60) days following the end of each reporting period. In addition, upon completion of the project, a Final Report shall be produced by the project and shall be submitted to the EU commission within sixty (60) days following the end of the last reporting period. This report shall contain necessary points according to the guidelines of the European Commission.

3.3 Project Meetings

3.3.1 WP Meetings

The WPL of each technical WP (WP2-WP5) is responsible for the organisation of bi-weekly virtual meetings that will last from the beginning to the completion of the WP. During these meetings, the partners involved in the WP provide the technical status and advances that have been performed within the WP, identifying issues/risks, listing down all the presentations and publications and ensure that they are reported to the dissemination document in WP6, and report the status of incoming deliverables.

3.3.2 F2F Meetings

The consortium will meet each three/four months, in person, to discuss all management and technical progress and issues, revise the status of the deliverables and the periodic reports. These physical meetings represent indeed the possibility to better exchange technical ideas to reach the objectives of the project, as well as to take important decisions.

Guidelines for hosting F2F meetings:

- The appointed meeting venue/location should be easily reachable. The hosting partner must provide information regarding meeting logistics (e.g., reaching the venue, travel information, and accommodation details).
- The hosting partner will cover the costs associated with the hosting of the meeting, while each participant will cover their own travel costs.
- The host must offer an appropriate meeting room, equipped with visual and audio infrastructure for facilitating the presentation of material. Moreover, the meeting room should offer access to the Internet.
- Although not obligatory, it is kindly recommended that the host provide water, coffee, and lunch during breaks, and organises a social event, such as a dinner.

3.3.3 Minutes of meetings

The chairperson will keep the meeting minutes, as well as any decisions made, in a formal record. Minutes should be kept for all meetings (i.e., virtual and physical ones) in an easy-to-read and compact form. The chairperson is also responsible to share the meeting minutes to the involved partners and to make them available for all partners in the official repository of the 6G-DISAC project.

4 Document handling

4.1 Documentation Templates

To ensure consistency across the project, the PC, in accordance with the PMT suggestions, provides a common layout of the documents, and a set of templates for the following types of documents:

1. Deliverables and internal technical reports
2. Presentations
3. Project progress updates
4. F2F meetings documents
5. Official reports

4.2 File and document naming

The PC, in accordance with the PMT, provides a unified convention for naming and version handling of files in the project:

- For deliverables and internal technical reports: 6G-DISAC_Dx.y.docx.
- For general presentations: 6G-DISAC_events_date.
- For F2F meeting folders: 6G-DISAC date venue.
- For F2F meetings presentations: 6G-DISAC_WP_event.

4.3 Dissemination quality

To ensure a high quality of the material disseminated by 6G-DISAC, all the material to be disseminated is reviewed by the PMT. This includes external presentations, reports, visualisation tools, etc.

4.4 Dissemination and communication requirements

All dissemination and communication activities, and any results funded by the project grant must include:

1. The EU emblem, and the following text: This work has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101139130
2. The 6G SNS logo.
3. Eventually, the 6g SNS IA logo.

4.5 Confidentiality

There are several identified levels for the confidentiality of the documents:

- Public documents: most of the 6G-DISAC deliverables are public in the description of work. Also, presentations from workshops or conference may be made available. One must note that only the final version of any public document is public.
- Confidential documents: some deliverables, internal reports, the minutes of the meetings are confidential. They nevertheless can be exchanged between partners by using the exchange server.
- Restricted documents: documents that include proprietary information and that cannot be shared with the whole consortium.

The level of confidentiality of a document must be mentioned on the first page. The Consortium Agreement rules the management of confidentiality and the non-disclosure obligations. One must note that the Advisory Board members do not belong to the consortium and must be considered in accordance regarding these confidentiality rules.

4.6 Disclaimer and copyright

Written material must include the disclaimer and copyright:

- Disclaimer: This document reflects the contribution of the participants of the research project 6G-DISAC. It is provided without any warranty as to its content and the use made of for any particular purpose.
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4.7 Publication rules

The agreement on the dissemination of the results in the form of scientific papers, as well as standard and regulatory contributions, are covered in the Consortium Agreement and will be followed accordingly. The relevant description is copied below:

“Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted, provided that no Confidential Information, Background or Results of other Parties is included in the publication.”

An example of the timing for conference/journal is given in Figure 4-1:

Figure 4-1 Submission timeline for conference and journal papers

Following the Grant Agreement, the 6G-DISAC consortium must provide *open access* for research results, as specified on the EC funding Sygma reporting platform:

“open access means the practice of providing online access to research outputs resulting from actions funded under the Programme, in particular scientific publications and research data, free of charge to the end-user.”

5 Quality assurance and Risk Management

5.1 Quality management

Although the handling of deliverable quality is covered in Section 3, quality must also be taken into account for the project process as a whole, to ensure that the project continues to be innovative, open to partnerships and forward-looking. As a result, the project's management process and developments will be periodically reviewed in light of:

- Maintaining attention to the project's goals, which include end-user requirements, and high-quality technical outputs.
- Project process improvement by recognising deviations and modifications, and by synchronising the connected project processes.
- Identification and assessment of actions and outcomes that would compromise the project's ability to fulfil its goals.

All partners are jointly responsible for quality assurance, used at all project activity levels. Expenses, resources, and schedules, i.e. technical and financial annexes to the EC GA, will be continuously monitored and controlled. Costs, resource, and schedule deviations must have

their underlying reasons determined, documented, and used as a basis for ongoing improvement. It is important to assess any potential effects of schedule modifications on the project's budget, resources, and level of output.

5.2 Risk management

To ensure the right interworking between the different project activities and phases, as well as between partners with different backgrounds, the management must be able to address and harmonize different aspects. Therefore, risk management is a high priority activity for the PMT, which will execute a risk management process according to the following key steps:

- High quality and ongoing project management based on past experiences;
- Identify the expertise of the individuals who influence these decisions;
- Create divergent, yet plausible, scenarios with underlying assumptions of how the work programme and task delivery might evolve;
- Develop action plans based on either the solutions, or the most desirable outcome towards which a company can direct its efforts;
- Monitor events as they unfold to test the strategic direction of the project;
- Be prepared to modify as required.

The risks related to implementation are also minimised by a detailed work package and task descriptions with clear contributions of the partners, by allocating enough resources per task, by defining and implementing the quality plan and the consortium agreement, by complementary expertise and roles of the project partners.

5.2.1 Risk management plan

The 6G-DISAC project adopts a four-stage risk management plan, for identifying, quantifying, responding and monitoring risks. Specifically, the iterative plan is:

1. Risk identification: the process of identifying risks related to the project documenting every potential threat.
2. Risk analysis: the quantification step providing an estimate of the potential repercussions to the project of the identified threats.
3. Risk response: the information gathered in the previous two stages is used in risk response development to create mitigation strategies, and take preventative measures.
4. Risk monitoring: update a record of potential threats, the execution of mitigation strategies is ensured, their effectiveness is quantified, and modifications are applied to the risk management strategy.

5.2.2 Critical Risk table

The preliminary list critical risks for the project implementation, along with their impact potentials and the relevant mitigation measures, are listed in Table 5-1. The consortium has identified and analysed a set of potential sources of issues, corrective actions, and special attentions to ensure the overall success of the project. The risks include (T) Technical and (MNG) Managerial risk, with associated probability and impact (selected from (VL) Very Low, (L) Low, (M) Medium, (H) High and (VH) Very High). PMT will continuously keep track of the potential new risks, thus the risk table will be consequently updated before each project meeting during the project execution time.

Table 5-1 Critical Risks

Risk	Type and WP affected	Probability and Impact	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Inadequate project or technical coordination.	Type: MNG WPs: WP1	Probability: VL Impact: VH	The management structure provides sufficient management resilience and proactive measures to avoid this risk. In addition, CEA (Project Manager) has proven experience in project coordination in national, international, and cross-continent project participation and coordination with specific experience in the framework of European projects. Moreover, CHA (Technical Manager) has had a wealth of experience in several large European initiatives.
Conflicts between partners.	Type: MNG/T WPs: WP1	Probability: L Impact: H	Many 6G-DISAC partners are represented through personnel with proven experience with European collaborations (industry and academic). In the case of conflicts, the PM team will intervene and moderate. The deep knowledge of the CEA team involved reduces notably this risk with opportunities for direct and clear action enabling fast and focused reactions.
A partner becomes deficient or entirely remiss in the execution of assigned obligations. Drop-out by a partner.	Type: MNG WPs: WP1	Probability: L Impact: H	Well-defined project management processes allow for early determination. The management team will proactively seek solutions through re-assignment of tasks or budget in the agreement with all project partners. Only reliable partners are part of the consortium. In the case of a drop-out of a partner, substitutes from the consortium are named and receive the allocated budget. Only if necessary, new partners will be recruited.
Specific expertise is missing or a key expert leaves Consortium.	Type: MNG/T WPs: all	Probability: VL Impact: M	The risk has been minimised by carefully selecting a top-level consortium which fits to the addressed challenges. If specific expertise is missing, the management team will either assign substitute partners, or appropriately re-focus activities and objectives. Almost all the partners are very large organisation with many key experts and with world class recruiting capability.
Lack of synchronisation between WP2-WP5. Joint activities, leading to delays or missed deadlines. Misalignment in models and assumptions. Solution design is not finished in time or incorporates design mistakes.	Type: MNG/T WPs: WP1, WP2-WP5	Probability: VL Impact: L	Regular progress monitoring by the management team will minimise the risk. The proposed work plan allows for sufficient flexibility to accommodate unexpected delays. Intermediate deliverables are foreseen to align and provide inputs in time, allowing continuous refinement of the technical work.
Project lifetime and target standardisation bodies might have not perfectly aligned agendas.	Type: T WPs: WP6	Probability: L Impact: L	NEC, Orange, TIM, CEA, Nokia, NKUA will actively contribute to key standards bodies and provide warnings in an early stage. Alternative bodies would then be identified by industrial partners.
Technical solutions cannot meet the related KPIs.	Type: T WPs: WP2, WP3, WP4	Probability: M Impact: H	WPs should warn in advance about deviations to escalate issues and plan appropriate recovery actions. Prioritisation of KPIs and use cases might occur in case all KPIs may not be fulfilled together.

Semantic approaches fail to provide expected performance gains.	Type: T WPs: WP3	Probability: M Impact: L	Each semantic sensing approach will be mirrored by a conventional model-based solution, so that there is back-up for waveform design and signal processing based on semantics. CEA have already a consolidated track record in semantic communications and PoC design on both NN semantic related modules and waveform design.
The complexity or energy footprint of the signal processing methods, resource allocation, or waveform optimisation is underestimated.	Type: T WPs: WP3, WP4	Probability: M Impact: M	WP3 and PW4 will evaluate the trade-off between performance and complexity/energy efficiency. Relaxation of the KPIs in collaboration with WP2 will be investigated.
Demonstrators do not achieve the KPIs as expected.	Type: T WPs: WP5	Probability: L Impact: VH	Demonstrators will be designed to target selected KPIs. Individual components will be carefully tested before the integration into the demonstrators and a quality assessment will be performed. In case of performance not in line with the expectations, an ad-hoc strategy will be applied to improve the performance or replace with alternative solutions. Testing phases will be iterative: a convergence will be reached when expected KPIs can be fulfilled.
Failure to set up and configure the testbed environment necessary to trial the use cases and proofs of concept.	Type: T WPs: WP5	Probability: L Impact: VH	BOS, NEC, NOK, RAD have already developed several trials on either communication or sensing, which will constitute the baseline for the 6G-DISAC trial. These existing hardware platforms have already been tested for various purposes, and also are continuously being maintained and updated with new features. The consortium has carefully reviewed their capabilities to support the selected use cases. Furthermore, the partners have extensive experience in setting up testbeds and carrying out experimental campaigns.